

Reduced Phenolphthalein as a Redox Indicator for the Titrimetric Determination of Hydrazine and Semicarbazide with Hexacyanoferrate(III)

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Reduced phenolphthalein has been successfully used as a redox indicator in the presence of copper(II) sulphate as a catalyst in the titrimetric determination of hydrazine and semicarbazide with hexacyanoferrate(III).

Hydrazine and its compounds, well known as active reducing agents in preparative organic and inorganic chemistry, are used in chemical analysis, mainly for the reduction of some metal cations. Titrations of hydrazine and its derivatives with hexacyanoferrate(III) have been reviewed in the literature^{1,2}. A variety of oxidimetric reagents in aqueous as well as concentrated acid media are reported in the literature^{3,4}. Some of the reagents like, for example, haloamines or related compounds reported are insoluble in water but are soluble in glacial acetic acid or organic solvents. In some other cases the titrations have to be carried out with the usual oxidants in fused medium. Comparatively recently dichlorobarbuturic acid has been reported⁴ as an oxidimetric reagent. However, this reagent carries with it, the limitation of accelerated deterioration from traces of water, light and heat. The determination of hydrazine with potassium dichromate reported by Mahamoud *et al.*⁵ requires elevated temperatures. Besides, the reaction needs a catalyst Cu^{2+} . The method uses a potentiometric end-point detection. The reaction between hydrazine and hexacyanoferrate(III) seems to require elevated temperature⁶ or osmium tetroxide or Zn^{2+} as catalyst⁷.

The present communication deals with the titrimetric determination of hydrazine and semicarbazide to a visual end-point with hexacyanoferrate(III) using reduced phenolphthalein at room temperature under the catalytic action of Cu^{2+} .

Results and Discussion

Preliminary experiments on the reaction of hydrazine with hexacyanoferrate(III) in 1.0 M alkali indicated that the reaction is not fast^{6,7}. Based on the earlier report⁵ Cu^{2+} is anticipated to exert a similar catalytic function in the titration of hydrazine with hexacyanoferrate(III). In experiments to check the catalytic effect of Cu^{2+} , 5.0 ml of hydrazine/semicarbazide, 1.0 ml of hexacyanoferrate(III) in a total 50 ml volume of 1.0 M alkali were taken. It was found that without addition of Cu^{2+} the yellow colour of hexacyanoferrate(III) persisted for 10 min. With 1.0 ml of hexacyanoferrate(III), 0.01 ml Cu^{2+} the colour persisted for 5 min and with 0.10 ml of Cu^{2+} the yellow colour disappeared instantaneously.

Good end-points were obtained at alkalinities ranging from 1.0 to 4.0 M NaOH in the presence of 0.10 to 0.30 ml of 1% Cu^{2+} solution at room temperature. The role played by Cu^{2+} is believed to be restricted to enhance the attainment of equilibrium⁸. Hexacyanoferrate(III) gives distinct red colour with reduced phenolphthalein. It was found to function satisfactorily in the titration of hydrazine and semicarbazide. 0.0646–0.3232 mmol of hydrazine can be determined to an accuracy of $\pm 0.15\%$, whereas the accuracy for semicarbazide is $\pm 0.6\%$ in the range 0.1325–0.3145 mmol. The reactions involved are

Experimental

Solutions of hexacyanoferrate(III) (0.1 M), semicarbazide (0.1 M), (both AnalaR), hydrazine sulphate (0.1 M), copper(II) sulphate (1%) (both proanalysis) were prepared in distilled water and standardized by recommended procedures^{1,9}.

Reduced phenolphthalein was prepared by zinc dust reduction. A mixture of phenolphthalein (0.5 g) and zinc dust (5 g) in 5 M NaOH (50 ml) was refluxed twice for 2 h each time and filtered. The filtrate was diluted to 50 ml with distilled water and kept in a dark bottle over a few granules of zinc.

Procedure for determination of hydrazine/semicarbazide: Standard hexacyanoferrate(III) (5 ml) was mixed with enough NaOH and water in a total volume of 50 ml such that the overall alkalinity was 1.0–4.0 M. To this 1% Cu^{2+} solution (0.30 ml) and indicator (0.50 ml) were added and titrated with hydrazine/semicarbazide solution. The change of colour from red to colourless indicated the end-point. The colour change at the end-point sharpened when the indicator was added after 75% of the titrant and involved no indicator error.

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NOTE

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